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Research Article

FORMULATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PIMECROLIMUS GEL FOR SYMPTOMATIC RELIEF OF ERUPTIVE XANTHOMAS

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Goshamahal Rd, near Nampally, Hyderabad, Telangana 500001**Abstract:**

The present study focuses on the formulation and development of a topical gel containing Pimecrolimus, aimed at providing symptomatic relief from eruptive xanthoma, a lipid metabolism disorder characterized by sudden eruptions of yellow-red papules. Given Pimecrolimus immunomodulatory properties and effectiveness in managing inflammatory skin conditions, it was chosen as the active pharmaceutical ingredient for gel formulation. The formulation was developed using Carbopol 934 as the gelling agent, along with excipients like polyethylene glycol, ethanol, methylparaben, and triethanolamine. Four formulations (F1–F4) were prepared and evaluated for various physicochemical parameters, including pH, viscosity, spreadability, drug content, and in vitro drug release. Among all, formulation F3 demonstrated optimal characteristics, showing a drug content of 92.52%, viscosity of 32,000 cps, and spreadability of 25.6 g-cm/sec. In vitro drug release studies using Franz diffusion cells indicated a sustained release of 95.55% over 8 hours. The gel also remained physically and chemically stable over three months under different storage conditions, as per ICH guidelines. Overall, the developed Pimecrolimus gel exhibited favorable topical application properties, effective drug release, and stability, making it a promising candidate for further clinical evaluation in the treatment of eruptive xanthoma.

KEY WORDS: Pimecrolimus, Eruptive Xanthoma, Topical Gel, Calcineurin Inhibitor, Carbomer, Triethanolamine, Drug Release, Franz Diffusion Cell, Skin Disorders, Gel Formulation, Stability Studies, In-vitro Evaluation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cosmetics are substances or products used to enhance or alter the appearance or fragrance of the body. According to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), cosmetics are defined as "articles intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, or sprayed on, introduced into, or otherwise applied to the human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance."¹ Transdermal drug delivery system is a therapeutic system of defined surface area that delivers a predetermined amount of drug to the surface of intact skin at a pre-programmed rate. These systems systemically provide drug at a predictable rate and maintain the rate for extended period, thus eliminating numerous problems associated with oral products such as, unpredictable or reduced bioavailability, enhanced first pass hepatic metabolism, relatively short residence time, dose dumping and dose inflexibility.² Gel is a substance that is formed by trapping liquid molecules within a solid or semi-solid network. In general, it consists of a small amount of solid dispersed throughout a larger volume of liquid, creating a structure that exhibits both solid-like and liquid-like properties. Gels can be found in everyday life in many forms, such as hair gel, gelatin desserts, and medical gels like ultrasound gel.³ Eruptive xanthoma is a lipid disorder manifesting as sudden eruptions of yellow papules, often associated with underlying metabolic conditions such as hyperlipidaemia. Due to the chronic and relapsing nature of the disease, patient

compliance with oral medications is limited. Topical gel formulations provide a convenient, non-invasive mode of treatment with targeted drug delivery and fewer systemic effects. Pimecrolimus, a novel anti-inflammatory and lipid-modulating compound, was selected for topical delivery in gel form to offer symptomatic relief and local action.⁴ To formulate and develop a topical Pimecrolimus gel for the symptomatic relief of eruptive xanthoma, ensuring enhanced drug delivery, stability, and patient compliance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS

Pimecrolimus procured from Hetero Labs, HYD. Carbopol 934 and PEG was obtained from Synpharma Research Labs, Hyderabad. Other chemicals and the reagents used were of analytical grade.

METHODOLOGY

FTIR Studies

Drug polymer interactions were studied by FT-IR spectroscopy. One to 2mg of Pimecrolimus and polymer and physical mixtures of samples were weighed and mixed properly to a uniform mixture. A small quantity of the powder was compressed into a thin semitransparent pellet by applying pressure. The IR spectrum of the pellet from 400-4000cm⁻¹ was recorded taking air as the reference and compared to study any interference.⁵

Formulation development

Table-1: Formulation table of in Pimecrolimus gel composition (%w/w)

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
Pimecrolimus	1	1	1	1
Carbopol 934	0.25	0.5	0.75	1
Polyethylene glycol	5	5	5	5
Ethanol	10	10	10	10
Methyl paraben	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Triethanolamine	2	2	2	2
Distilled water	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Formulation of Gel⁶

Procedure:

Step 1: Preparation of the gel base

- Weigh an appropriate quantity of Carbopol 940 and disperse in distilled water under continuous stirring using a magnetic stirrer.
- Allow the dispersion to hydrate and swell overnight or for a minimum of 2 hours.

Step 2: Drug solubilization

- Dissolve Pimecrolimus in an ethanol

Step 3: Incorporation of the drug

- Add the solubilized drug into the hydrated gel base with continuous stirring to ensure uniform distribution.

Step 4: pH adjustment

- Adjust the pH to 6.0–7.0 using Triethanolamine to obtain a clear and homogenous gel.

Step 5: Addition of other excipients

- Add methyl paraben and stir to uniformity.

Step 6: Final weight adjustment and packaging

- Make up the final volume with distilled water and pack in suitable containers.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS**Physical appearance**

The color, odour, taste of the drug was observed.⁷

Clarity:

The formulations were visually checked for the clarity.⁸

Measurement of pH

The pH of various gel formulations was determined by using digital pH meter. One gram of gel was dissolved in 100ml distilled water and reserved for 2 hours. The measurement of pH of each formulation was done in triplicate and average values are calculated.⁹

Drug content

1 gm of the prepared gel was mixed with 100ml of desolved solvent. Aliquots of different concentration were prepared by suitable dilutions after filtering the stock solution and absorbance was measured.¹⁰

Spread ability

It indicates the extent of area to which gel readily spreads on application to skin or affected part. The therapeutic efficiency of a formulation also depends upon its spreading value Spread ability is considered in terms of time in seconds taken by 2 slides to slip off from gel which is placed in between the slides under the direction of certain load, if the time taken for the separation of two slides is lesser, then spread ability will be better.¹¹ It is calculated by using the formula.

$$S = M.L/T$$

M= weight tied to upper slide

L= length of glass slide

T= time taken to separate the slides

Viscosity study

The measurement of viscosity of the prepared gel was done with a brook field viscometer. The gels were rotated at 0.3, 0.6 and 1.5 rotations per minute. At separate speed, the coinciding dial reading was noted. The viscosity of the gel was calculated by multiplication of the dial reading with factor given in the brook field viscometer catalogues.¹²

In vitro diffusion studies

The diffusion studies of the prepared gels can be carrying out in Franz diffusion cell for studying the dissolution release of gels through a cellophane membrane and the diffusion studies were carried out at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ using 250ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as

dissolution medium. 5ml of each sample was withdrawn periodically at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8hrs and each sample was replaced with equal volume of fresh dissolution medium. Then the samples were interpreted for the drug content by using phosphate buffer as blank.¹³

Kinetics of drug release studies¹⁴

The quantitative elucidation of the values obtained in the dissolution study is facilitated by the usage of a generic equation that mathematically translates the dissolution curve in function of some parameters related to the gel. For understanding the mechanism of drug release and release rate kinetics of the drug from dosage form, the Invitro drug dissolution data of optimized formulations obtained was fitted to various mathematical models such as zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix and Korsmeyer-Peppas's models.

Zero order kinetics

Drug diffusion from pharmaceutical dosage forms that do not disaggregate and release the drug slowly can be represented by the following equation:

$$Q_0 - Q_t = K_0t$$

Arrangement of equation yields: $Q_t = Q_0 + K_0t$

Where Q_t is the amount of drug dissolved in time t ,

Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution (most times, $Q_0 = 0$)

and K_0 is the zero-order release constant expressed in units of concentration/time.

To study the release kinetics, data obtained from in vitro drug release studies were plotted as cumulative amount of drug released versus time.

First order Kinetics

The equation for first order release is given below

$$\log Q_t = \log Q_0 + K_1t/2.303$$

Where,

Q_t is the amount of drug released in time t ,

Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution

and K_1 is the first order release constant.

A graph of the decimal logarithm of the released amount of drug versus time will be linear. gel following this diffusion profile release the drug in a way that is proportional to the amount of drug remaining in its interior, in such way, that the amount of drug released by unit of time diminishes.

Higuchi model

Higuchi described drug release as a diffusion process based on the Fick's law, square root time dependent. The simplified Higuchi equation is represented as

$$Q_t = Kt^{1/2}$$

Where,

Q_t = amount of drug released in time t ,

K = Higuchi's constant

A linear relationship between amount of drug released (Q_0) versus square root of time ($t^{1/2}$) is observed if the drug release from the topical gel is diffusion controlled.

Korsmeyer-Peppas model

This mathematical model, also known as the Power Law, has been used, very frequently; to describe the drug release from several different pharmaceutical modified release dosage forms. The Korsmeyer-Peppas model relates drug release exponentially to time. It is described by the following equation

$$M_t/M_\infty = at^n$$

Where 'a' is a constant incorporating structural and geometric characteristics of gel, 'n' is the release exponent, indicative of the drug release mechanism, and the function of 't' is M_t/M_∞ (fractional release of drug).

Stability studies¹⁵

For all the pharmaceutical dosage forms it is important to determine the stability of the dosage form. This will include storage at both normal and

exaggerated temperature conditions, with the necessary extrapolations to ensure the product will, over its designed shelf life, provide medication for absorption at the same rate as when originally formulated. The design of the formal stability studies for the drug product should be based on the knowledge of the behaviour and properties of the drug substance and formal stability studies on the drug substance.

Storage Conditions

- Accelerated: $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75 \pm 5\%$ RH
- Intermediate: $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/65 \pm 5\%$ RH
- Long term: $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/60 \pm 5\%$ RH

Testing Intervals for

- Accelerated: Initial, 1, 2, 3 months

The optimized in situ gel were stored at $45 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ in hot air oven, over period of three month. At the end of three-month gel were tested for *in-vitro* release profiles. Stability studies were conducted as per ICH guidelines. Samples were taken at 3 months intervals for *in-vitro* release estimation. The *in-vitro* release results were suggesting that there was no significant change in *in-vitro* drug release.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

FTIR Studies:

Fig-1: FTIR Spectra of Pimecrolimus

Fig-2: FT-IR graph for optimized formulation

Compatibility studies were performed using IR spectrophotometer. The IR spectrum of pure drug and physical mixture of drug and excipients were studied. The characteristic absorption of peaks were obtained as above and as they were in official limits ($\pm 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) the drug is compatible with excipients.

Evaluation parameters

Physical Appearance

The prepared Pimecrolimus gel was found to be white, homogenous, smooth, and free from grittiness. The formulation showed good aesthetic appeal and uniform consistency suitable for topical application.

Clarity test

The formulated all formulation kept under for visual observation. The prepared formulations were found to be free from any suspended particulate matter.

pH

The pH of the gel was found to be in the range of 5.6 to 6.1, which is compatible with the skin's natural pH.

Table-2: pH values of all formulations

Formulation code	pH
F1	5.6
F2	5.9
F3	6.1
F4	5.8

Viscosity

Viscosity was evaluated using a Brookfield viscometer and found to be 28,000–32,000 cps, indicating a stable gel structure with adequate adherence to the skin, yet not too viscous to hinder spreadability.

Table-3: Viscosity values of all formulations

Formulation code	Viscosity (cps)
F1	28000
F2	30000
F3	32000
F4	29000

Spreadability

The spreadability of the gel was within the acceptable range, measured as 25.6 g-cm/sec, indicating good ease of application and uniform coverage over the skin surface.

Table-4: Results of spread ability of all formulations

Formulation code	Spreadability (gm.cm/sec)
F1	29.1
F2	27.8
F3	25.6
F4	26.9

Drug content:

The drug content uniformity ranged from 89.68% to 92.52%.

Fig-5: Results of drug content of all formulations

Formulation code	Drug content
F1	91.66
F2	89.68
F3	92.52
F4	90.24

In-Vitro dissolution studies

In vitro drug release studies were conducted using Franz diffusion cell with phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The cumulative percentage drug release over 8 hours was found to be 95.55%. The formulation provided sustained release, suitable for prolonged action.

Fig-6: Results of gel of all formulations

Time (hours)	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	15.96	17.49	18.46	16.39
2	27.48	29.67	29.13	27.85
3	33.36	35.68	37.49	38.16
4	46.98	47.18	48.46	49.52
5	55.86	57.82	58.94	59.86
6	65.50	66.79	67.48	64.53
7	79.85	78.59	79.67	76.39
8	92.36	93.65	95.55	94.58

Fig-3 : Drug release studies of all formulation

Drug release kinetics

Zero order kinetics

Fig-4: Zero order kinetics of optimized formulation

First order kinetics

Fig-5: First order kinetics of optimized formulation

Higuchi model**Fig-7: Korsmeyer peppas of optimized formulation****Stability studies:**

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the gel formulation F-3 after 3 months. Parameters quantified at various time intervals were shown.

Table-7: Results of stability studies of optimized formulation F-3

F. Code	Parameters	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-3	25 ⁰ C/60%RH % Release	95.55	94.58	93.67	92.17	Not less than 85 %
F-3	30 ⁰ C/75% RH % Release	95.55	94.37	93.60	92.35	Not less than 85 %
F-3	40 ⁰ C/75% RH % Release	95.55	94.35	93.19	92.25	Not less than 85 %

CONCLUSION:

The study aimed at formulating a topical gel containing Pimecrolimus for the effective management of eruptive xanthoma, a lipid-associated skin condition. The gel was successfully prepared using Carbopol 934 as the gelling agent, and evaluated for its physicochemical properties, drug

release profile, and stability. Overall, the developed Pimecrolimus gel demonstrated favourable characteristics for topical use and showed potential to provide symptomatic relief in eruptive xanthoma through localized, sustained delivery of the active agent. Further clinical evaluation is recommended to confirm its efficacy and patient acceptability.

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